

SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS RELATED TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC PROJECTS

by

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INTRODUCTION

The EU's Green Deal aims to increase its manufacturing capacity and support its clean tech industry and supply chains. The Critical Raw Material Act (CRMA) is the main Regulation (EU 2024/1252) for the establishment of a framework for ensuring a secure and “sustainable” supply of critical raw materials (CRMs). It includes a list of CRMs that are important for the European economy and face a high risk of supply disruption. The CRMA aims to ensure that European extraction, processing and recycling of strategic raw materials (SRMs) meet 10%, 40% and 25% of EU's demand by 2030, respectively. For example, lithium, cobalt, nickel, manganese and graphite are needed for the manufacture of batteries for e-mobility and energy storage, while rare earth elements (REEs) are required for the manufacture of motors of electric vehicles and wind turbines. The same day CRMA entered into force, the Commission published a call for submission of proposals for recognition of projects as Strategic Projects (SPs). On March 25, 2025, the Commission adopted 47 SPs (Fig. 1), for the extraction, processing, recycling or substitution of SRMs, to substantially improve its domestic capacities and strengthen the European raw materials value chain by modifying and broadening the sources of supply. These projects have cross-border benefits beyond the EU Member State concerned.

The 47 projects will be implemented in 13 Member States, namely Belgium, Czechia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Poland, Romania, Spain, and Sweden. They cover 14 of the 17 SRMs (bismuth, silicon metal and titanium metal were not covered by SPs in the first list) mentioned in the CRMA, while 25 projects involve extraction activities, 24 processing, 10 recycling and 2 substitutions of raw materials. 22 of these projects are related to lithium, 12 to nickel, 10 to cobalt, 7 to manganese and 11 to graphite, elements that are important for the EU battery raw material value chain. Also, one project involves magnesium and three involve tungsten that may contribute to the resilience of the EU's defence industry. These projects are an important milestone in the implementation of the CRMA and if initiated as planned and completed successfully will contribute to Europe's green and digital transitions, and also support several industrial sectors including aerospace, renewable energy, electronics, defence

Strategic Projects for the EU

Fig. 1. Location of SPs for the extraction, processing, recycling or substitution of SRMs in the EU (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_864).

and transport. The capital investment needed so that SPs become operational exceeds €22.5 billion. Their successful implementation requires the coordinated support by the Commission, Member States and financial institutions, including the European Investment Bank (EIB), the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) / Cohesion Fund, and private financial institutions).

IMPORTANT SOCIO-ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECTS – ISSUES OF CONCERN

It is known that the Social License to Operate (SLO) / Public Acceptance (PA) is an informal social contract that emerged some 30 years ago to bridge the gap between the mining industry and the society by incorporating the principles of Global Mining Initiative (GMI) (Komnitsas 2020, Ruokonen 2020). SLO/PA will be a major challenge during the entire life cycle of the SPs and will depend on several factors of varying importance for different projects; these may include among others the type of the ore extracted / metal produced, the associated land uses, the previous practices (if any) of responsible mining, the response to mining accidents / the taking of responsibility and the rehabilitation / compensation actions planned, the level of education and quality of life in the areas of concern (involving health care, energy price, state of the environment), the trust in regional / central government and the relations among all involved stakeholders (Eerola & Komnitsas 2025).

Resilience Directive under the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030, that is part of the European Green Deal.

- Assessment of environmental and socio-environmental impacts, through LCA and S-LCA studies to define that SPs fully meet the sustainability requirements; emphasis should be given on minimization of water and energy consumption, especially in remote and sensitive areas.
- Future SPs should target the increased contribution of recycled materials to raw materials demand – end-of-life recycling input rates (EOL-RIR).
- Strategic Partnerships between the EU and third countries must comply with the highest environmental and social standards. In November 2023, the EU signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Government of Greenland for a strategic partnership to develop sustainable raw materials value chains, however the recent US claims over Greenland, Canada and other countries may result in geopolitical developments.

Finally, an important pending issue is the selection and implementation of SPs located in third countries, providing that they comply with the criteria set in article 6 of the CRMA. The Commission received 46 applications after the first call and the list of the selected projects will be announced at a later stage. However, special emphasis needs to be taken because some of them, as the Jadar Valley Li project in Serbia, sparked major protests and fierce opposition, also due to the fragile political situation in the country, that resulted in cease of activities more than three years ago. In this specific case, public opposition and social unrest were intensified since July 2024 when the Serbian Constitutional Court overturned a 2022 government decision that had annulled initial planning permissions. Recently a letter backed by signatures of 100,000 citizens was given to the Delegation of the EU in Serbia urging the EU not to grant strategic status to the Jadar project. This opposition is most probably one of the reasons that the EC has not yet disclosed the list of third-country SPs. The Jadar Valley Li project is critically presented in a recent documentary film (Storyrunner/SIM² KU Leuven 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

SPs for the extraction, processing, recycling and substitution of SRMs aim to substantially improve the capacities of EU's industry and strengthen the European raw materials value chain. The successful completion of SPs requires SLO / PA and the highest level of transparency in all stages of their implementation. CSR as well as ESG are crucial aspects for all interested stakeholders. Also, the set-up of an accurate risk management plan will identify early-stage potential risks and assist in the implementation of well-established and efficient remediation measures. The establishment and independent monitoring of quantitative, where possible, technological, economic, environmental and social Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), will be crucial for the development of trust between the industry and all interested stakeholders as well as the timely completion of SPs. The results of LCAs and S-LCAs will also contribute to this direction. This approach will answer to a certain degree the accusations made by NGOs and other environmental groups that CRMA is largely based on extractivism, exacerbates the depletion of mineral resources and therefore results in severe environmental impacts and deterioration of the quality of life in affected areas and for future generations.

Projects selected in this call as well as future SPs should focus on recycling and increased life cycle of (electronic) components and equipment to reduce the need

The SPs will benefit from streamlined permitting and access to finance. The Commission confirms that for SPs in line with the CRMA, the permit-granting process will not exceed 27 months for extraction projects and 15 months for other projects. However, the acceleration of the procedures may raise concerns that may cause legal implications, public opposition and finally delays; currently, the permitting processes can last from five to 10 years. The Commission also confirms that all projects will be implemented by following all environmental, social and governance (ESG) standards, thus streamlined procedures will not imply lower standards on environmental assessment or reduced involvement of the public. Thus, all SPs will be subject to environmental assessments and public consultation requirements.

The quality of all environmental media (soil/water/air) and the conservation of nature must be non-negotiable criteria. A single case of contamination / accident may spark protests and threaten the implementation also of other SPs. The technical and financial feasibility of SPs also need to be clearly justified. To increase transparency, the SPs must maintain a regularly updated website that provides detailed information to all relevant stakeholders and mainly the local population on the projects' progress, impacts and benefits; also, their interaction with local communities must be clearly demonstrated.

Special attention needs to be paid in case projects affect minorities / indigenous people and their land or are implemented in sensitive areas or areas of specific environmental and cultural importance (UNESCO World Heritage sites, biodiversity hotspots, and (sub)arctic ecosystems). The poor sensitivity shown in some cases in the past by industry in addressing social and environmental issues has often led to violent conflicts. The lessons learned so far by all stakeholders are most probably the best guide for the development of an efficient and transparent roadmap, involving several well-established milestones that will monitor the progress made by the SPs and also safeguard the future activities which may be revised when needed. The implementation of life cycle assessment (LCA) and social LCA (S-LCA) studies to quantify greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, energy use associated with all stages of SPs, water consumption and re-use as well as the social impact, involving human health and well-being, land use, social justice, economic stability and prosperity, is crucial for the development of trust among the industry and the involved stakeholders (Bartzas & Komnitsas 2024, Souza et al. 2025). Overall, some of the most important aspects for the successful implementation of SPs include:

- Increased transparency during the implementation phase; there are accusations that no access to documents was allowed by the public during the screening / selection stage, but this is how the evaluation process is carried out; several of the submitted documents contain confidential information and personal data that cannot be disclosed to the general public and other industries.
- Update of mining legislation pertinent to the management of waste from extractive industries (Directive 2006/21/EC amending 2004/35/EC); it is known that in several (third) countries management of wastes is carried out according to different standards (e.g., for the construction of tailing dams, the disposal of wastes, the collection, treatment and release of leachates to water reservoirs / streams). It is believed that the management of mining wastes according to the EU's Best Available Technologies (BAT 2018) will improve the prestige and image of the industry.
- Update or revision, if needed, of other related EU legislation including, the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), the Birds Directive (2009/147/EC), the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and the proposed Soil Monitoring and

for the extraction of CRMs as much as possible. The EU may also set benchmarks for the next 10–20 years, for efficient use of resources, responsible mining, valorisation of wastes for the production of high added-value materials, minimization of environmental impacts as well as efficient communication between the policy makers, the industry and all involved stakeholders in the raw materials sector.

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